

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-133-IG-5% RAC	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	13	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 133
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 11:26:21 AM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 5:12:10 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.963	116803	7.54	13281
2	6.602	646340	41.73	62084
3	7.172	669039	43.20	60143
4	11.185	116525	7.52	5763

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-88-IG-5% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20221119
Vial:	7	Acq. Method Set:	5%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 88
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	15.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/19/2022 9:35:03 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 5:13:46 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.967	69542	2.65	8305
2	6.581	2534105	96.43	247241
3	7.166	9129	0.35	1049
4	11.023	15151	0.58	906